

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN PRIMARY EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Aziza Hayitova

student at Karshi State University

Abstract

The original concept considered in this work is to point out the role of parental participation in their child's primary education.

This study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What is parental involvement itself?!
2. Why parental caring is crucial for education?!
3. How school administrations in Uzbekistan can involve parents to their child's education?!

Jane D. Hull says: "At the end of the day, the most overwhelming key to a child's success is the positive involvement of parents." [] Parental involvement in education is the parents' role in their child's learning and it aids learners to achieve good behaviour, development of their academic knowledge and gaining success at school. With parents' assistance children can adapt to the school life easily and they also aid young learners to strengthen what they have learnt at school. Especially it should be stressed that, some of the ways for involving parents into primary education are also offered.

Education system in Uzbekistan is compulsory for eleven years beginning with primary education that lasts four years (Grade 1-4) and involves children from the age of six to eleven (Shaturaev, 2021d). 'Then it keeps going by two phases of secondary education taking five and two years respectively' (Habibov, 2012). Kindergartens are examples of preschool education and it is not compulsory. Although some children attend to the kindergartens, they may face to some difficulties at the first stage of school due to their lack of learning abilities such as bad memory, problems in their comprehension, language development challenges, short attention span, lack of communication skills, difficulties in self-control and so on. According to statistics, 8.849 kindergartens opened in Uzbekistan in 2021 and 190 of them are state preschool educational institutions, 120 non-state and 8,539 are family kindergartens [6]. In the rural areas of Uzbekistan there is a shortage of state and non-state kindergartens so that most of the population could utilize family members. However, not all such kind of family kindergartens have enough knowledge or qualification to give children preschool education and prepare them for primary education. Although teachers give primary knowledge to young learners, they need mostly their

parents' help because children accept their teachers as strangers and when they do not understand something, they may be embarrassed to ask it from their teacher.

Parental involvement is defined by Grolnick and Slowiaczek (1994) as 'the devotion of reforces by the parent to the child within a given domain'. They mentioned three types of involvement in children's schooling, such as 'behaviour, cognitive-intellectual and personal' (1994). However, another scientist Joyce Epstein (1995) [1] outlines six concrete types of family

**THE KEYS TO SUCCESSFUL
SCHOOL-FAMILY-COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS
EPSTEIN'S SIX TYPES OF INVOLVEMENT**

	PARENTING: Assist families in understanding child and adolescent development, and in setting home conditions that support children as students at each age and grade level. Assist schools in understanding families.
	COMMUNICATING: Communicate with families about school programs and student progress through effective school-to-home and home-to-school communications.
	VOLUNTEERING: Improve recruitment, training, work, and schedules to involve families as volunteers and audiences at school or in other locations to support students and school programs.
	LEARNING AT HOME: Involve families with their children in learning activities at home, including homework, other curriculum-related activities, and individual course and program decisions.
	DECISION MAKING: Include families as participants in school decisions, governance, and advocacy through PTA/PTO, school councils, committees, action teams, and other parent organizations.
	COLLABORATING WITH COMMUNITY: Coordinate resources and services for students, families, and the school with businesses, agencies, and other groups, and provide services to the community.

involvement, namely nurturing model, two-way communication between parents and teachers, parents as volunteers, studying at home and being actively involved in decision-making and collaboration with the community in affirming school program (Picture:1). Fan and Chen (2001) [2] say that parental involvement has a positive effect on students' academic performance and is also a crucial aspect for the remedy of many problems in education. They also add that one fundamental way in which parents can transmit the cultural value of education is becoming involved in their child's schooling. Fan and Chen (2001) [2] further indicate that 'parental involvement in education rotates around three main constructs, like supervision, communication and parental expectation..

Picture:1

Early stages of school can be tricky for the young learners. It is both teachers' and parents' duty to give a hand to them in this situation. First major issue for children at school is adaptation

to the school life: new friends, new knowledge and also the new atmosphere. Parents can increase their child's interests for school by giving positive opinions about the school life and benefits of education, they can introduce the teacher and explain his role for children's education, they can tell their own funny stories among classmates in their school period and so on. Young learners may face to problems related to their studies, classmates or other types and it is parents' role to explain the situation appropriately and what to do in this position.

As an early age child may struggle with learning new lessons, such as mathematics, reading, learning foreign languages, correct and beautiful writing and so on. Teacher educates young learners new knowledge: explains the themes or rules, aids to improve their learning with utilizing several teaching methods, sometimes works individually with children who struggle with learning any subject after the lessons. Nevertheless, consolidating the knowledge studied at school occurs with an assistance of parents. Some children have bad memory not remembering the lesson or the teachers' explanation clearly when they go home or when they are doing homework. Then there may appear a demand for explaining all over again which should be done by parents. When children go home after the lessons, parents should ask what new things they have learnt at school today and also should help their children to do home tasks. All of these express that the student success is achieved with the help of both teachers and parents. At the same time, more people in Uzbekistan consider that only teachers are responsible for children's education. However, most of the support and movement towards good learning should be done by parents.

Although it seems that most of the responsibility in education is on the teachers' personal duty, it cannot have escaped anyone's notice that children spend more than half of their day at home, with their family. Duration of the lessons in Uzbekistan is 45 minutes and the duration of the break between classes — 5 — 10 minutes (the duration of the break between the school day — 15 — 30 minutes) [3]. There are average 5 lessons a day that take 225 minutes and average number of breaks is 5 (every break is 5 minutes, only after the third lesson it is 15 minutes, all over 35 minutes). Overall, one day at school takes about 260 minutes (about 5 hours). So, parents are responsible for the rest of the day.

Owing to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, educational institutions in Uzbekistan continued their work online. So did schools. Pupils were educated online and they were assessed through the website "kundalik.com". In spite of the fact that schools returned to traditional way of teaching later, they have been still using online journals for marking and parents also should check this program and see their child's grades. Nevertheless, most parents say that they have no any technologies or internet connection for visiting the site and this task is obviously done by

teachers themselves as there is a punishment for them or they are rebuked if the parental involvement of their class gains low rate. This situation is graded as teacher does not work with the parent but some parents do not want to work with a teacher since they seem themselves as very busy people at work or they see teachers at a lower rate than themselves. So nowadays one of the most essential issues of primary education in Uzbekistan is how to involve parents in their child's early school education and there are some options for solving this problem.

Firstly, school authorities in Uzbekistan should make an opportunity for the parents not only to take part and observe the lessons, but also to watch and grade their child's participation in the lessons. There is no need to come every day but they can do it when they want. If any learner has lack of knowledge or activity in class, parents should blame themselves. Because, the teacher gives the same knowledge to the whole class, and the problem mentioned above occurs when parents do not work with their children at home.

Another advantageous way to involve parents in young learners' education is to establish tasks or activities that should be done with parents at home. If the learner has a difficulty in any subject, teacher can give extra explanation or do activities together until the learner is able to do it independently. Then the teacher can give extra tasks to the learner for doing at home and designates to ask for help from parents if there is any misunderstanding. If parents do not understand the task, they can ask it from the teacher by calling and after the teachers' instructions, they can help the learner. However, if parents reject to work with their children, it causes academic failure. Learner considers this subject very difficult and lose interest on it, too.

The next way for attracting parents' attention to their children's education is that, schools should mark every parents' involvement in their children's studies. Marks can be put according to how the learners do their home tasks, how well they learnt the previous lessons or how well they memorized new vocabularies and other activities that they have done with their parents. The most active and caring parents should be awarded by the school administrations at the end of every month. As a result, children get proud of their parents and try to be as them.

In conclusion, it seems to improve parental involvement in primary education as parents have a leading role in their children's education. With an assistance of parents, learners can achieve both academic and life success. Parents are motivators and models for the young learners. On this basis, we conclude that importance of parental involvement should be explained firstly to the parents themselves and some ways offered above for involving parents to primary education should be used. It will be important if future research investigate the usage of these offers and their results.

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